

LONG-TERM BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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A two-parameter Weibull distribution was used to analyze the stress-rupture lifetime data spanning over 8 years for Kevlar 49/epoxy and S-glass/epoxy composites. The results show that, in S-glass/epoxy, a random failure process prevails regardless of the level of applied stress. However, in Kevlar 49/epoxy, the failure above 80% UTS is controlled by initial defects while, below 80% UTS, a wear-out type of failure process is observed. A similar wear-out process also dominates the stress rupture at elevated temperatures. Therefore, a time-temperature reduction can be carried out by using an Arrhenius type of equation.

INTRODUCTION

The stress-rupture behavior of composite materials is one of the most important engineering properties especially where a long-term sustained loading is expected as in pressure vessels. The generation of such long-term lifetime data requires not only effort but also time which cannot be compromised easily. In this paper we present the analyzed results of the long-term lifetime data for Kevlar 49/epoxy and S-glass/epoxy composites.

Stress-rupture properties of composite strands have been extensively studied by Chiao et al. [1-5]. The composites chosen were S-glass/epoxy [1], beryllium wire/epoxy [2], Aramid fiber/epoxy [3,4] and graphite/epoxy [5]. Further updated results are summarized in [6]. The effect of elevated temperature on stress-rupture behavior of Kevlar 49/epoxy was studied in [7].

In the present paper we analyze the data available as of June 1979 for 3 types of Kevlar 49/epoxy composites and 2 types of S-glass/epoxy composites, using a two-parameter Weibull distribution. An expanded version of the elevated-temperature data of Ref. [7] is analyzed to develop a method of accelerated testing based on an Arrhenius type of equation. Also, an attempt is made to interpret the underlying failure processes through statistical analyses of lifetime data.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The types of fibers and epoxy compositions used are listed in Table 1 together with the cure cycles. In each composite, fiber strands were impregnated with epoxy, and were wound on racks, using a filament-winding machine. After cure the strands were cut from the racks and stored in plastic tubes. The resulting fiber volume content ranged from 60 to 70%.

<u>Material System</u>	<u>Fiber</u>	<u>Epoxy Composition</u>	<u>Cure Cycle</u>
A	Kevlar 49, nominal 380 denier with 280 filaments	DER 332/T403 (100/45)	24 h @ 25°C + 16 h @ 85°C
B	PRD-49-III, preproduction version of A	ERL 2258/ZZL 0820 (100/30)	3 h @ 93°C + 2 h @ 163°C
C	Same as A	XD 7818/XD 7575.02/ XD 7114/Tonox 60-40 (50/50/50/35.8)	3 h @ 70°C + 3 h @ 120°C
D	S-glass, single end yarn	DER 332/ERL 4206/ Epi-Cure 855 (70/30/40)	16 h @ 177°C
E	Same as E	DER 332/T403 (100/36)	16 h @ 25°C + 24 h @ 77°C
F	Same as A	Same as B	Same as B

Table 1. Material systems studied

Before mechanical testing, aluminum tabs were bonded to ends of ~~5~~ strands, leaving a gauge length of 25.4 cm.

All static tensile tests were carried out at room temperature on a universal testing machine at a strain rate of $\sim 5\%/min$. Failure loads were converted to fiber strengths, using the net cross-sectional area.

Stress-rupture tests were performed on dead-weight loading stations. Composites A and C were tested in a controlled room where the ambient temperature was maintained between 22 and 24°C and relative humidity was 10%, with extremes of 6 and 20% on rare occasions. Also, the room was kept dark unless lights were necessary. Composites B, D and E were tested in a different room where the environment was not so well controlled; the normal temperature ranged between 22 and 28°C with extremes of 9 and 41°C as the result of equipment failure. The relative humidity usually fluctuated from 24 to 37% but with extremes of 10 and 56%. Composite F was tested at elevated temperatures 100, 110, and 120°C. Further details of specimen preparations and test conditions can be found in [1,3,7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Strength

The in situ ultimate tensile strengths (UTS) of fibers are shown in Fig. 1 for composites A through E. The numbers inside parentheses represent the number of specimens tested. As expected, the S-glass fibers in composites D and E exhibit higher strength than the Kevlar 49 fibers in composites A through C. The coefficient of variation ranges from a low of 2.5% to a high of $\sim 5\%$. The average in situ UTS of the Kevlar 49 fiber in composite F was 3.36 GPa.

Fig. 1. Ultimate tensile strengths (UTS) of fibers in various composites

Stress Rupture at Room Temperature

Since the publication of Refs. [1,3,6,7] additional lifetime data have been obtained. These data were analyzed by using a two-parameter Weibull distribution of the form

$$R(t) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (1)$$

where α and t_0 are called the shape parameter and characteristic lifetime respectively. $R(t)$ is the probability of surviving time t .

The parameters α and t_0 were determined by using the method of maximum likelihood [8]:

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r t_i^\alpha \ln t_i + (n-r) t_s^\alpha \ln t_s}{\sum_{i=1}^r t_i^\alpha + (n-r) t_s^\alpha} - \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r \ln t_i \quad (2)$$

$$t_0 = \left[\frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r t_i^\alpha + (n-r) t_s^\alpha \right]^{1/\alpha} \quad (3)$$

where t_i : experimental lifetimes
 t_s : lifetime of last failure
 n : total number of samples
 r : number of failed samples.

Experimentally, median ranks were used for $R(t)$. Suppose t_i is the i th lifetime. The probability of survival $R(t_i)$ at t_i is then given by a median rank,

$$R(t_i) = 1 - \frac{i-0.3}{n+0.4} \quad (4)$$

The results available as of June 1979 are summarized in Table 2. At each stress level, at least 45 strands were tested to provide a high reliability. The shape parameters and characteristic lifetimes are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively, as functions of applied stress. In the figures the open symbols indicate that the parameters are from incomplete data ($r < n$).

The shape parameter provides a valuable information as to the underlying failure processes. The failure rate λ , which represents the probability of failure per unit time interval, is given by

$$\lambda = - \frac{dR/dt}{R} = \frac{1}{t_0} \left(\frac{t}{t_0} \right)^{\alpha-1} \quad (5)$$

Thus the failure rate can increase, remain constant, or decrease depending on whether α is greater than, equal to, or smaller than unity. An increasing failure rate indicates that the underlying failure process is a wear-out process whereas a decreasing failure rate is indicative of failures being controlled by initial defects. In case of random failures the failure rate remains constant [9].

Referring back to Fig. 2, we see that for the S-glass/epoxy composites the shape parameter remains constant around unity regardless of applied stress level. Thus the underlying failure process is one of random failure.

For Kevlar 49/epoxy composites, however, the shape parameter increases from below unity to above unity as applied stress is lowered. Thus the failure process changes from one of defect-controlled failure at higher stresses to a wear-out failure at lower stresses.

Composite	Applied stress, % UTS	Total number of samples	Number of failures	Last failure time, h	Shape parameter	Characteristic lifetime, h
A	86	94	94		0.766	4.731×10^1
	80	101	69	3011	1.226	2.639×10^3
	74	96	57	9253	1.339	9.763×10^3
	68	95	3	8141	1.433	8.967×10^4
	50	No failure as of 6/4/79				
B	90	101	101		0.926	9.899×10^{-1}
	87	100	100		0.963	3.941×10^0
	84	103	103		0.913	2.204×10^1
	80	100	100		1.084	2.156×10^2
	70	49	49		2.015	9.907×10^3
	60	47	38	51168	3.371	4.303×10^4
	50	45	4	65976	2.534	1.684×10^5
C	90	72	72		0.522	3.675×10^0
	87	67	67		0.601	1.505×10^1
	85	61	61		0.466	3.851×10^1
	83	73	73		1.098	1.788×10^2
	80	64	64		1.471	7.150×10^2
D	83.6	201	201		0.831	4.765×10^{-1}
	75.6	201	201		0.851	1.127×10^1
	65	101	101		1.008	9.479×10^2
	57.9	51	44	70584	0.995	3.165×10^4
	50	88	39	73224	0.988	1.221×10^5
	40	50	1	39720		
	33	47	1	64056		
E	81.3	100	100		0.919	1.374×10^0
	74.6	101	101		0.902	1.542×10^1
	70	99	99		0.931	6.010×10^1

Table 2. Lifetime characteristics at room temperature

From Fig. 2 we also see that, at lower stresses, the Kevlar 49/epoxy composites exhibit more of a wear-out type of failure than do the S-glass/epoxy composites. This may be because glass fiber is brittle while Kevlar 49 fiber is tough. In this regard, we note that a larger shape parameter also means a smaller scatter, i.e., a smaller coefficient of variation. Thus, at lower stresses, the lifetimes of the Kevlar 49/epoxy composites show less variability than those of the S-glass/epoxy composites.

Relations between applied stress and characteristic lifetimes are shown in Fig. 3. In the range of applied stresses shown, the Kevlar 49/epoxy composites are superior to the S-glass/epoxy composites. However, the Kevlar 49/epoxy B shows a steeper decrease in applied stress for characteristic lifetimes larger than 10^4 hours.

With time many fibers were seen strayed off the surfaces of strands. The longer a strand survives, the more fiber separations it showed. The same difference was also observed after final failure between strands tested in stress rupture and those tested in quasi-static tension, the former showing more extensive fiber separations. Thus, there is much more extensive matrix failure in sustained loading environment than in quasi-static tension.

For the Kevlar 49/epoxy composites, the underlying failure process seems to change depending on whether applied stress is above or below 80% UTS. Above 80%

Fig. 2. Shape parameters

Fig. 3. Characteristic lifetimes

UTS, however, the shape parameter is larger than unity and the stress-lifetime relations become steeper. Thus, we can conclude that the stress rupture at stresses above 80% UTS is controlled by initial defects while these defects play a secondary role at lower stresses. At higher stresses, a fiber break has more tendency to propagate normal to the fibers [4], and hence initial defects will have a more direct influence on lifetime. Note that these defects include not only geometrical flaws but also weak fibers.

Comparing various Kevlar 49/epoxy composites in Fig. 3, we see that composite A has longer characteristic lifetimes than composite B. Furthermore, composite B shows a downturn near 70% UTS. Differences in the materials used and in the test environments could lead to different stress-lifetime relations. First, the PRD-49-III fiber in composite B is a preproduction version of the Kevlar 49 in composite A. Second, the epoxy system used in composite B has about 50% higher strength than the epoxy in composite A, while the moduli are comparable [10,11]. Finally, as mentioned earlier, the test environment for composite A was controlled better than for composite B, one of the differences being that strands of composite B were exposed to fluorescent lights continuously while only an occasional exposure was allowed for strands of composite A.

The downturn in Fig. 3 exhibited by composite B is likely to have been caused by the exposure of the strands to fluorescent lights, and higher temperature and humidity fluctuations. Composites A, C and F did not suffer any appreciable reduction in strength after up to 3 1/2 years of storage when shielded from lights in a well-controlled room [12]. However, strands of composite B showed about 15% reduction in strength after 2 3/4 years of storage in the room where stress-rupture tests were in progress [6]. Thus, we conclude that a combination of ultraviolet light exposure from fluorescent lights and a more unfavorable temperature and humidity can cause additional damage especially with time. In this regard we note that Kevlar 49 fiber absorbs light in the ultraviolet region, and such absorption can cause degradation of strength [13,14].

Stress Rupture at Elevated Temperatures

The results of stress-rupture tests at three different temperatures are listed in Table 3. Applied stresses are given as a percentage of the room-temperature mean strength.

The shape parameters are plotted against applied stress in Fig. 4. Unlike the room temperature (RT) data, the shape parameters at elevated temperatures (ET) do not depend on the applied stress in a consistent manner. Also, there does not appear to be any correlation between the temperature and the shape parameter if the room temperature data at 86% UTS are excluded.

The RT shape parameters at 80% and below for composite A are comparable to the ET shape parameters, indicating that the underlying failure processes are basically the same except for the time scale involved. The differences in time scale can be seen from Fig. 4 which shows relations between applied stress and logarithmic lifetimes at different temperatures. In the figure the open symbols represent the characteristic lifetimes in Tables 2 and 3. The closed symbols are reserved for the characteristic lifetimes based on a joint shape parameter to be discussed later. In any case, the stress-lifetime relations are quite linear, and furthermore, parallel to one another.

As discussed earlier, at room temperature the effect of stress concentration caused by failure of weak or defective fibers is not significant at lower stresses because substantial matrix failure is possible along the fibers. At an elevated temperature the same type of subcritical failures can occur at higher stresses because the matrix is weaker.

The foregoing observations indicate the possibility of pooling all the ET data and the RT data for composite A except at 86% stress level. First, the shape parameter for all the data can be obtained by using the method of maximum likelihood estimate.

Temperature, °C	Applied stress % UTS	Total number of samples	Shape parameter	Characteristic lifetime, h
100	85.5	46	2.071	1.702×10^{-1}
	80.4	53	1.354	7.562×10^{-1}
	73.2	76	1.093	4.798×10^0
	67.2	58	1.520	5.448×10^1
110	85.5	39	2.101	1.045×10^{-1}
	80.4	75	2.448	2.987×10^{-1}
	73.2	76	1.326	2.133×10^0
	67.2	54	1.689	2.305×10^1
	56.4	59	2.244	2.847×10^2
120	85.5	48	1.493	3.802×10^{-2}
	80.4	43	2.065	1.943×10^{-1}
	73.2	80	1.647	1.439×10^0
	67.2	73	1.877	8.040×10^0

Table 3. Lifetime characteristics of composite F at elevated temperatures

Fig. 4. Shaper parameters at elevated temperatures

Suppose we have m groups of data, each group consisting of n_i samples. Here the subscript i denotes a group. Thus, in the i th group the lifetimes are denoted by $\{t_{i1}, t_{i2}, \dots, t_{in_i}\}$. Then, the joint shape parameter is given by [15]

$$\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left[\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} t_{ij}^{-\bar{\alpha}} \ln t_{ij}^{-\bar{\alpha}}}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_i} t_{ij}^{-\bar{\alpha}}} - \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \ln t_{ij} \right] \quad (6)$$

The corresponding scale parameter for each group is easily obtained as

$$t_{oi} = \left[\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} t_{ij}^{-\bar{\alpha}} \right]^{1/\bar{\alpha}} \quad (7)$$

The joint shape parameter determined from Eq. (6) is

$$\bar{\alpha} = 1.643 \quad (8)$$

The scale parameters from Eq. (7) are shown in Fig. 5 as closed symbols.

Fig. 5. Characteristic lifetimes at elevated temperatures

Figure 6 shows all the ET data after normalization with respect to appropriate scale parameters t_{oi} . The curve represents Eq. (1) with α replaced by $\bar{\alpha}$. A similar comparison between Eq. (1) and the room-temperature data is shown in Fig. 7. For the amount of data involved, Eq. (1) with $\bar{\alpha}$ can represent the data fairly well.

An investigation of the dependence of the scale parameter t_{oi} on the applied stress and temperature can be facilitated by noting that the failure processes in composites can conveniently be described by using a material age τ [16]. The material age is like a strain-hardening parameter in plasticity or crack length in fracture mechanics. In composites it may represent the fraction of broken fibers. The material age is different from real time; a material may age only if an external load is applied.

Since aging is certainly a rate process, the rate of aging in stress rupture can be assumed to depend on the ratio σ of the applied stress to the mean strength and temperature T through an Arrhenius type of equation [17]

Fig. 6. Elevated-temperature lifetime data normalized on the basis of joint shape parameter

Fig. 7. Room-temperature lifetime data of composite A normalized on the basis of joint shape parameter. The data at 86% UTS has been excluded.

$$\frac{d\tau}{dt} = A \exp [-(E - B\sigma)/kT] \quad (9)$$

where E is the activation energy, k is the Boltzmann constant, and A and B are material constants. The lifetime distribution of Eq. (1) then follows if we choose the probability of survival at τ as

$$R(\tau) = \exp (-\tau^\alpha) \quad (10)$$

Substituting τ from Eq. (9) into Eq. (10) and comparing the resulting equation with Eq. (1), we obtain a relation between σ and t_o :

$$\sigma = -2.3 \frac{kT}{B} \log t_o - 2.3 \frac{kT}{B} \log A + \frac{E}{B} \quad (11)$$

A comparison of Eq. (11) with Fig. 5 suggests that B is proportional to T,

$$B = \frac{2.3}{m} kT \quad (12)$$

Therefore, Eq. (11) can be written as

$$\sigma = -m \log (t_o/a_T) + b \quad (13)$$

where

$$-\log a_T = \frac{E}{2.3k} \left(\frac{1}{T_R} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$b = m \left(\frac{E}{2.3kT_R} - \log A \right) \quad (15)$$

and T_R is the room temperature (= 296 K).

In Fig. 5, $(-\log a_T)$ is the horizontal distance between the room-temperature line and the one at T. The measured distances are plotted against $1/T$ in Fig. 8. The relation between $(-\log a_T)$ and $1/T$ is quite linear as expected from Eq. (14). The resulting values of m , b and E/k are respectively given by

$$\begin{aligned} m &= 8.01 \times 10^{-2} \\ b &= 1.065 \\ E/k &= 11.11 \times 10^3 \text{ K} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The master relation between applied stress and the reduced lifetime t_o/a_T is shown in Fig. 9.

In Ref. [7] an equation similar to Eq. (11) was used to analyze the ET data and the RT data of composite B. However, no assumption was made as to the shape parameter being independent of temperature. Also, B was assumed to be a constant. Since the variation of the elevated temperature was over a rather small range, the available data do not seem sufficient to distinguish between the two approaches. Yet, within the framework of Eq. (11), the RT data of composite A can be blended more readily into the ET data.

CONCLUSIONS

Lifetime data of Kevlar 49/epoxy and S-glass/epoxy composites spanning over 8 years have been analyzed by a two-parameter Weibull distribution. The possibility of time-temperature reduction through an Arrhenius type of equation has also been explored. The following conclusions are drawn from this study.

1. Stress rupture of S-glass/epoxy composite is controlled by a random failure process regardless of the level of applied stress. The logarithmic characteristic lifetime is linearly related to the applied stress.

2. The failure process in stress rupture of Kevlar 49/epoxy composites depends on the applied stress. Above 80% UTS, the failure process tends to be controlled by initial defects. Below 80% UTS, however, a wear-out type of failure prevails.

Fig. 8. Time-temperature reduction factor a_T versus temperature

Fig. 9. Master relation between applied stress and reduced time

3. There is a strong indication that a stress-free aging is important especially in long-term stress-rupture tests of Kevlar 49/epoxy composites. Effects of exposure to ultraviolet light, temperature and humidity need further investigation.

4. The failure process at elevated temperatures in Kevlar 49/epoxy composites is similar to the long-term failure process at room temperature, i.e., at lower stresses. Thus, a time-temperature reduction is possible through an Arrhenius type of equation.

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